

Linking long-term patterns of landscape heterogeneity to changing ecosystem processes in the Kruger National Park, South Africa

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OBJECTIVE 1: IDENTIFYING PATTERNS OF LANDSCAPE HETEROGENEITY METHODS FLOWCHART

SNAPSHOTS OF CLASSIFICATION RESULTS

Scatterplot matrix of bands 1-4 in 2008 illustrates correlation between bands

SO WHAT?

The natural self-organising arrangement of patches in the landscape is an expression of landscape structure and function. The resulting patterns should guide management and research planning in protected areas. The challenge lies in identifying a method capable of classifying these patterns and generating ecologically meaningful results.

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